

5. A higher magnification view of the interrupted region in the sclerenchymatous tissue (S). X 250.

6. Diagram showing the Passage of air (arrows) through the interrupted regions of the sclerenchymatous tissue at the junction point between culm and roots.

free flow of air, the junction points between the culm and the root were examined with the use of serial glycol methacrylate sections. The sections show that the layer of sclerenchymatous tissue is not continuous, but is interrupted at places by aerenchymatous cells (Fig. 3, 4, and 5) with large intercellular spaces. Within these intercellular spaces or "air passages," air coming from the shoot could easily diffuse as depicted diagrammatically in Figure 6.

Thus, morphologically, there are continuous "air passages" from the culm to the root in the rice plant. ■

Leaf rolling and unrolling behavior in relation to soil moisture tension and climatic factors

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Rolling and unrolling of rice leaves are common symptoms of drought. The leaves remain open in the morning, roll severely at noon, then unroll in the afternoon. This behavior in relation to soil moisture stress and climatic factors was investigated under field and greenhouse conditions.

Nine pure line rice varieties belonging to the aus group (local early varieties grown as dryland broadcast paddy) were grown under dryland conditions in the field in March 1979 for 30 days with proper irrigation, then the water supply was stopped to expose them to high soil moisture tension (SMT). The SMT was measured by gypsum blocks at 8-10 cm and 12-15 cm soil depths. The degree of leaf rolling and water saturation deficit (WSD) and SMT were recorded when the varietal differences in terms of leaf rolling became distinct at noon.

All the varieties had no to slight symptoms of leaf rolling in the morning and in the afternoon. But at noon, they differed significantly in degree of leaf rolling even though the SMT during morning, noon, and afternoon was similar (see table). It appeared that the

Soil moisture tension at 3 different times measured by gypsum blocks installed at two soil depths, Bangladesh.

Soil depth (cm)	Gypsum block no.	Soil moisture tension (bars) at		
		0830 h	1230 h	1730 h
8-10	1	-6	-6	-6
	2	-2	-2	-3
	3	-2	-2	-2
	4	-1	-1	-1
	5	-3	-3	-3
12-15	1	-1.5	-1.8	-1.8
	2	-0.8	-0.8	-0.8
	3	-1.5	-1.5	-1.5
	4	-0.3	-0.3	-0.3
	5	-1.0	-1.0	-1.0

degree of the plant's internal moisture stress determined the rolling and unrolling of rice leaves in the field. The WSD percentage of rice leaves was considered the index of the plant's internal moisture stress, and was positively associated with degree of leaf rolling (see figure).

During the time of observation, the air temperature was 25°C in the morning and 35°C at noon and in the afternoon. Relative humidity was 98% in the morning, 53% at noon, and 43% in the afternoon. Solar radiation was 0.37 cal/cm² per minute in the morning, 1.00 cal/cm² per minute at noon and 0.25 cal/cm² per minute in the afternoon. The observations indicate that the amount of available solar radiation is perhaps the most important factor determining the WSD of rice leaves and, consequently, the degree of leaf rolling.

To quantify the contribution of solar radiation, temperature, and relative

Relationship between degree of leaf rolling and water saturation deficit (%). Leaf rolling scale: 1 = none or slight symptom, 5 = severely rolled.

humidity to WSD of rice leaves, the diurnal change of WSD of the three upper leaves of BR8 was determined under high SMT in the greenhouse from 0600 to 1800 hours at 2-hour intervals. The solar radiation, temperature, and relative humidity were also recorded. The relationship between average WSD of the three upper leaves and the three climatic components is shown by the following equation:

$Y = 4.437 + 8.324 X_1^{**} + 0.087 X_2^{ns} + 0.018 X_3^{ns}$
where Y is WSD, X_1 is solar radiation, X_2 is air temperature, and X_3 is relative humidity. The value of R^2 was 0.97. The equation indicates that available solar radiation significantly determined the change of WSD in this experiment. The percentage contribution of solar radiation, temperature, and relative humidity

to WSD was 71.6, 17.6, and 10.9.

The results explain rolling and unrolling of rice leaves at high SMT. Rice

leaves roll severely at noon because of high internal moisture stress caused by bright sunshine. In the morning and in

the afternoon they remain open because of lower WSD caused by lower solar radiation. ■

Rice-based cropping systems

Success with old rice seedlings

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In parts of North India, temperature is low during ripening of rice and young seedlings transplanted late yield low. The transplanting begins and continues at different ages depending upon the farmers' resources (irrigation, labor, machinery, etc.). An experiment was conducted to assess the yield variation that results from transplanting seedlings at different ages and to explore the possibility of averting yield reduction through the use of seedlings from sparsely seeded puddled nurseries (25 and 50 g seed/m² vs the 100-g/m² recommended practice). The rice variety was Jaya. A randomized block design with 3 replications was used. The nursery was sown on 9 June 1976, seedlings were transplanted at 25, 35, 45, and 55 days old at 20 × 15-cm spacing. Seedlings were uprooted with the Khurpi so that there was minimum injury to the seedlings, particularly the old ones. Care was also exercised to ensure that all the shoots of the old seedlings were included when transplanted at 2 seedlings/hill. Thus, 2, 3, 4.5, and 5.5 shoots/hill were transplanted at 25, 35, 45, and 55 days age, respectively. Nitrogen fertilizer was applied to the nursery at 100, 125, 150, and 175 kg N/ha for the different ages. In the main field, the crop was fertilized with 120 kg N/ha.

The yield reductions caused by transplanting old seedlings were small and nonsignificant (Table 1). The yield was 11% lower in 55-day-old seedlings than in 25-day-old. Ripening occurred during 16-27 October (Table 2) and the crop was exposed to a mean maximum air temperature of 31.5°-32.2°C and to a

Table 1. Grain yield of rice variety Jaya as influenced by seedling age and seeding rate in nursery, 1976.

Seedling age (days)	Grain yield (t/ha) at seeding rate of			Mean
	25 g/m ²	50 g/m ²	100 g/m ²	
25	8.00	8.25	7.82	8.02
35	7.67	7.74	7.87	7.76
45	7.68	7.54	6.99	7.40
55	7.34	7.26	6.85	7.15
Mean	7.67	7.70	7.38	

Treatment	S.Em. 1	C.D. 5%
Seedling age	181	Nonsignificant
Seed rate	157	Nonsignificant
Interaction	315	Nonsignificant
C.V. %	7.2	

minimum temperature of 17.3°-15.2°C (cold), respectively. Aged seedlings (45 and 55 days) experienced more cool weather than the young seedlings (25 and 35 days). Using well-grown seed-

Survey of farmers' rainfed and irrigated cropping patterns in Bangladesh

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A survey of the cropping patterns followed by farmers in Bangladesh was conducted by BRRI and the Directorate of Agriculture (Extension and Management), Government of the Peoples' Republic of Bangladesh, to prepare inventories of the existing cropping patterns under rainfed and irrigated conditions. A questionnaire was sent to the Extension Officer/ Agriculture Officer of each *thana* (5th-level administrative unit) of the country. A total of 186 thana responded to the survey.

In the rainfed areas, the cropping

Table 2. Date of maturity of rice variety Jaya as influenced by seedling age and seeding rate in nursery, 1976.

Seedling age (days)	Date of maturity when Jaya was seeded at		
	25 g/m ²	50 g/m ²	100 g/m ²
25	16Oct	16 Oct	18 Oct
35	21 Oct	22 Oct	23 Oct
45	22 Oct	24Oct	26 Oct
55	24Oct	26 Oct	27 Oct

lings from sparse nurseries (25 g seed/m²) was 7.3% more advantageous than using seedlings from dense nurseries (100 g seed/m²). Thus, reasonably high yields can be obtained from 55-day-old seedlings, with slight reduction in yield, provided the seedlings are well managed and uprooted with the least injury and 5-6 well-developed shoots are transplanted in each hill. ■

intensity was 100-300%. The most common cropping pattern reported by 100 thana was jute - transplanted aman rice (t. aman) - rabi crops (winter crops: oilseeds, potato, wheat, tobacco). The next most common pattern reported by 87 thana was aus rice (mainly a direct-seeded crop) - t. aman rice - rabi crops (wheat, *panicum* sp., oilseeds, pulses, spices). Among the double-cropping patterns reported were jute - rabi crops (63 thana), jute - t. aman rice (30 thana), and aus rice - t. aman rice (18 thana). Single cropping of aus rice, t. aman rice, B. aman (deepwater) rice, potato, oilseeds, vegetables, and spices was also reported for the rainfed areas.

The survey revealed that in the irrigated areas, farmers practiced single, double, and triple cropping. Aus rice - t. aman rice - rabi crops (wheat, potato, oilseeds, winter vegetables, tobacco, etc.) was the most common cropping pattern (178 thana), followed by the aus rice - t. aman rice - boro rice pattern (108